

Original Article

Evaluate Personality Disorders Symptoms In Different Individuals

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Abstract

A personality disorder is a disorder described by unchangeable patterns of thinking, feeling, or disclose to others that causes problems in personal, communal, and work situations. They are characterized into three types: those characterized by odd/eccentric behavior, those characterized by suspenseful/erratic behavior, and those characterized by anxious/inhibited behavior. (catalog) BPD is widely diagnosed up to 20% of psychiatric patients have the borderline personality disorder, and it may occur in up to 2% of the general population. Biological and environmental factors are both implicated in the improvement of antisocial personality disorder. A survey was conducted in city of lights Karachi to ascertain the knowledge of building a character or how to build a character. The Personality Disorder test was administered by 500 persons who included mostly students, some Physicians, some older persons and single and married persons from age below 20 -above 30. The questionnaire was based on MCQs asking people to give fair opinion about what they feel about their emotion dysregulation, impulsivity, risk-taking behavior, irritability, feelings of emptiness, suicide, self-injury and fear of abandonment, as well as changeable interpersonal relationships. Thus, this study examined the temporal dynamics of emotions, self-esteem, anger, social relationships with others and ability speaks about your rights. Some of the questions asked by us included: They have difficulty in trusting others, His/her need is more important than others, Usually Mood swings, Feeling Depressed. This survey study show that personality disorder is mostly seen in females of age between 20 - 30.

Keywords

Personality Disorders, Suicidal thoughts, Self-Harming, Mood swings, ADHD

Purpose of study

To know the personality disorder in normal individual and how PD effect their lives.

Introduction

People vary in the ways that they view themselves and others, secure in relationships. It is quite common for these characteristics to periodically inhibit with a person's skill to cope with life, and may also lead to difficulties in social communications. When these difficulties are severe and endless, and when they lead to significant personal or social problems, they are described as personality disorders. (Nic Alvin, et al. 2006) Personality disorders are common situation in our society. Epidemiological estimates suggest that between 5% to 13% of people living in the community have problems that would meet the diagnostic criteria for PD (Coid, J et al., 2006) Among 30% to 40% of psychiatric out-patients and 40% to 50% of psychiatric in-patients are thought to meet the principles for PD.8 Some 50 to 78% of prisoners have been found to have PD.(Casey p. 2000) Risk of suicide and accidental death is high and it is predicted that between 47% to 77% of people who commit

suicide have PD.(Moran & Alvin ,2002, 2006)Suicide rates in prison remain many times higher than for the normal population. Because some people with PD enroll in dangerous way of acting, they have a higher risk of abnormal or accidental death. (Martin, Cloninger, et al 1985) Personality disorders are over the most frequent of psychiatric disorders, and they regularly co-exist with each other as well as with other psychiatric disorders. (Oldham , et al. 1995) having no psychiatric disability appeared in an OR for life span substance reliance of 1.0; having one disorderliness 2.7, two disorders 3.9, and three or more shambles 9.1 (95% CI). (Glantz el at., 2009)Therefore, having a psychiatric disability at all and/or having more than one psychiatric disorder occur to increase the relative risk for life span individual dependence. A personality disorder is a disorder described by unchangeable patterns of thinking, feeling, or disclose to others that causes problems in personal, communal, and work situations. They are characterized into three types: those characterized by odd/eccentric behavior, those characterized by dramatic/erratic behavior, and those characterized by anxious/inhibited behavior. (Widiger, 2006). The personality disorders are highly

comfort; if a person has one, it's likely that he or she has others personality disorder as well. Also, the number of people with personality disorders is predicted to be as high as 15% of the population. (Grant et al, 2004) PD characterized into clusters. (American Psychiatric Association. 2000)

Cluster A: Odd/eccentric (schizotypal, Paranoid and schizoid)

Schizotypal: weird manners of speaking or dressing. They have difficulty to forming relationships. May react strangely in conversation, not answer back, or talk to self. Speech elaborate or difficult to follow. (It may be a mild form of schizophrenia) (Mayo clinic staff, 2016)

Paranoid: suspicion in others. Apart to challenge the honesty of friends and read hateful intentions into others' actions. Flat to anger and aggressive outbreak but otherwise emotionally cold. Often jealous, over careful, reserved, overly serious. (Bressert, S. 2016)

Schizoid: Extreme self-questioning and withdrawal from relationships. Wish to be alone, little interest in others. Self-opinionated, distant, fantasizer. Fearful of close to others, with poor social skills, often seen as a "loner". (mayo clinic staff 2016)

Cluster B: Erratic/ Dramatic (Antisocial, Histrionic, Narcissistic, Borderline)

Antisocial: conscience History of betrayal, crime, legal problems, emotional and cruel behavior. Regret for hurting others. Cautious, careless, insensitive. At high risk for substance exploitation and alcoholism.

Histrionic: steady attention seeking. Egoistic language, inspirational dress, melodramatic illnesses, all to gain attention. Believes that everyone loves him. Affecting, lively, overly dramatic, fascinated, and excessively flirty. (American Psychiatric Association, et al., 2014)

Narcissistic: show feel of self-importance, absorbed by fantasies of self and success. Overestimate own achievement, Imagine others will recognize they are great. Good first impressions but poor longer-term relationships. Dishonest to others. Borderline: unsteady moods and extreme, stormy personal relationships. Self harm or suicidal threats. Self-image variation and an ability to see others as "all good" or "all bad."

Cluster C: Inhibited/Anxious (Avoidant, Dependent, Obsessive-compulsive)

Avoidant: psychologically anxious and distressed except for he or she is assured of being liked. In comparison with schizoid person, thirst for social communication. Fears disapproval and fear about

being abashed in front of others. Avoids social communication due to fear of rejection.

Dependent: Obedient, dependent, requiring Extra approval, Help, and advice. Be true to people and worried in losing them. Lacking self-confidence. Depressed when alone. May be suicidal if separation is threatened.

Obsessive-compulsive: careful, well behaved, perfectionist. Extra need to do everything correct. Fear of failure can make this person accurate and controlling. Less expression of emotions.

Borderline personality disorder is a continued disorder of personality followed by mood swings, unstable personal relationships, and identifying problems and it is generally associated with suicide. Since 1980, the year of the initial similarity of the criteria for personality disorders are indicated that BPD is clearly more common in women than men. According to the most recent edition of the book. (Rhee & Waldman, 2002) there is a 3:1 female to male gender ratio. Biological and environmental factors are both implicated in the improvement of antisocial personality disorder (Huesmann, et al., 2007) Biological abnormalities include low autonomic activity during stress, schizophrenia, right hemisphere abnormalities, sexual disorder, biochemical imbalances and reduced gray matter in the frontal lobes. (Lyons-Ruth et al., 2007) People with schizotypal personality disorder are usually termed as odd, if any, nearest relationships. They usually don't understand the result of their behavior on others. They establish expressive mistrust of others. These problems may start to serious anxiety and a set to turn incoming in social setting. (mayo clinic staff 2011) Schizoid personality disorder is a state in which people avoid social actions and normally shy away from inter-communication with others. They also have a finite range of emotional verbalization. (mayo staff 2016) Narcissistic personality disorder is a psychological disorder in which people have a bloated sense of their self-importance, extra need for adoration and a lack of pity for others. But afterwards this mask of over-confidence lies a weak self-esteem that's sensitive to the smallest judgment. (mayo staff 2014) All of the personality clusters have been recorded in case with element offense, with unfriendly personality usually being the most frequent; borderline personality is commonly the second most frequent cacciola et al., 2001)

We all have different manners of thinking, feeling and behaving and these are the segments that make us who we are, our personality. We don't always behave

in the same way, as our thinking, feelings and behaviors will often depend on the situation. But most of the time, we behave in totally a predictable way, or pattern. These patterns are those that make up our personality and express us as kind, shy, selfish, ambitious, and loving and so on. (Memiah limited 2016)

Methodology

A survey was conducted in city of lights Karachi to ascertain the knowledge of building a character or how to build a character .The Personality Disorder test was administered by 500 persons which included mostly students, some Physicians, some older persons and single and married persons from age below 20 -above 30, to determine the rate of personality disorder in Pakistan .The questionnaire was based on MCQs asking people to give fair opinion about what they feel about their emotion dys-regulation, impulsivity, risk-taking attitude, irritability, feelings of emptiness, suicide, self-injury and fear of abandonment, as well as changeable interpersonal relationships. which shows more prevalent in the general community than previously thoughts, and thus represents an important public health issue. Thus, this study examined the temporal dynamics of emotions, self-esteem, anger, social relationships with others and ability speak about your rights.

Result

The personality diagnostic questionnaire is a self-report questionnaire derived from personality disorder section. The survey based study of personality disorder symptoms have produced inconsistent results, the result show that the females most affected by personality disorder i.e.: 78% female and 22% males affected by personality disorder shows in fig 1. By the help of survey this is observed that in the age of 20-30 mostly females affected i.e.: 39% whereas 22% males affected in this age which shows in fig 2. The survey showed that mostly people have difficulty to trust the people which show paranoid personality disorder i.e.: 41% people have difficulty, 28% people have no difficulty and 31% people sometimes feel difficulty to trusting on people which shows in fig 3. Those people that thinks that their needs are most important than others have narcissistic personality disorder. In this survey 27% people say yes, 46% people say no and 27% people say sometimes which shows in fig 4. Mood swings, depression, afraid of being alone, thoughts of suicide and self-harming are the symptoms of borderline personality disorder. We observed that in people mood swings are most common i.e.: 42% that show in fig 5 and few people have depression i.e.: 41% that show in fig 6. The highly educated people not think to suicide or self-harming by frustrated to life. Therefore, in our survey mostly people say no thoughts for suicide i.e.: 70% and for no self-harming are 64% that show in fig 8 & 9.

Figure 1

Age wise PD patient

Figure 1

Trust Problems

Figure 2

Importance of Need

Figure 3

Mood Swings

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Discussion

A survey study which was conducted in the city Karachi in which many people participated and according to result people have difficulty in trusting others, they are afraid of being alone, they get depressed without a reason, sometimes they feel uncomfortable in a social gathering and try to avoid people these all are leading factors to destroy a person personality. which can lead to disorders in the person. (John M. Grohol, Psy. D. 2016) Personality disorder are circumstances in which an individual vary significantly from an average person, in terms of how they think, feel or relate to others.

As the results show that among male and females mostly females between age 20-30 affected by disorders of personality. In a person personality different types of disorder can be developed. As we collected data we saw people facing fear of trusting others which can be symptoms leading towards paranoid personality disorder, among the participates there were people who thinks to fulfill their needs firstly and then of others those people are affected with narcissistic personality disorder, there were people fighting with stress , depression and uncontrollable emotions and also cases of suicidal attempt were seen by people those people are affected by borderline personality disorder and commonly people were facing symptoms of borderline personality disorder in this survey

participants are those who fear of being alone are affected with dependent personality disorder.(mind.org. 2016) Despite of all of these types of disorders this studied shows that people are dealing with various faults in their character which need to be corrected by creating different schemes or test to polish their personality.

Conclusion

This survey study show that personality disorder is mostly seen in females of age between 20 -30. The result shows that people are facing through paranoid personality disorder and borderline personality disorder that is they have problem of trusting people, mood swings and depression mostly. survey study concluded that majority of people have personality disorder of age between 20 -30 due to stress, bipolar disorder, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), brain tumor and fear and genetically etc.

References

- Nic Alwin, Ron Blackburn, Kate Davidson, Maggie Hilton, Caroline Logan & John Shine. 2006 Understanding Personality Disorder: A Professional Practice Board Report by the British Psychological Society. Published by The British Psychological Society, St Andrews House, 48 Princess Road East, Leicester LE1 7DR.
- Coid, J. (1998) Axis 2 disorders and motivation for serious criminal behaviour, in Psychopathology and

- Violent Crime (ed. A.E. Skodol), American Psychiatric Association, Washington DC, pp. 53–96. Coid, J., Yang, M., Roberts, A. et al. (2006a)
- Casey, P. (2000) The epidemiology of personality disorders. In Tyrer, P. (ed.) *Personality Disorders: Diagnosis, Management and Course*. London: Wright, 2nd edition pp 71-79
 - Moran P., Walsh E., Tyrer, P., et al., (2003) The impact of co-morbid personality disorder on violence in psychosis – data from the UK 700 trial. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 182. 129-13
 - Martin, R., Watson, D., & Wan, C. K. (2000). ...Review of factor analytic studies of temperament measures based on the Thomas-Chess structural model: Implications for the big five. In C. F. Halverson, G. A. Kohnstamm, & R. P. Martin (Eds.),
 - Oldham JM, Skodol AE, Kellman HD, Hyler SE, Doidge N, Rosnick L, Gallaher PE. Comorbidity of axis I and axis II disorders. *Am J Psychiatry*. 1995; 152:571–578.
 - Glantz MD, Anthony JC, Berglund PA, et al. Mental disorders as risk factors for later substance dependence: estimates of optimal prevention and treatment benefits. *Psychol Med*. 2009; 39:1365–1377.
 - Widiger, T.A. (2006). Understanding personality disorders. In S. K. Huprich (Ed.), *Rorschach assessment to the personality disorders. The LEA series in personality and clinical psychology* (pp. 3–25). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
 - Grant, B., Hasin, D., Stinson, F., Dawson, D., Chou, S., Ruan, W., & Pickering, R. P. (2004). Prevalence, correlates, and disability of personality disorders in the United States: Results from the national epidemiologic survey on alcohol and related conditions. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 65(7), 948–958.
 - MayoClinic staff/ diseases-conditions of schizotypal-personality-disorder 2016
 - Bressert, S. (2016). Paranoid Personality Disorder Symptoms. *Psych Central*. Retrieved on September 29, 2016 Last reviewed: By John M. Grohol, Psy.D. on 17 Jul 2016
 - MayoClinic on diseases-conditions of schizoid-personality-disorder 2016
 - American Psychiatric Association Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth Edition, Revised National Institutes of Health, National Library of Medicine
 - Last reviewed 11/24/2014
 - Rhee, S. H., & Waldman, I. D. (2002). Genetic and environmental influences on anti-social behavior: A meta-analysis of twin and adoption studies. *Psychological Bulletin*, 128(3), 490–529. Twin and adoption studies suggest a genetic predisposition (Rhee & Waldman, 2002), Rhee, S. H., & Waldman, I. D. (2002).
 - L. Rowell Huesmann and Lucyna Kirwil Why Observing Violence Increases the Risk of Violent Behavior by the Observer 2007
 - Lyons-Ruth, K., Holmes, B. M., Sasvari-Szekely, M., Ronai, Z., Nemoda, Z., & Pauls, D. (2007). Serotonin transporter polymorphism and borderline or antisocial traits among low-income young adults. *Psychiatric Genetics*, 17, 339–343; Raine, A., Lencz, T., Bihle, S., LaCasse, L., & Colletti, P. (2000). Reduced prefrontal gray matter volume and reduced autonomic activity in antisocial personality disorder. *Archive of General Psychiatry*, 57, 119–127.
 - MayoClinic staff on diseases-conditions/schizotypal-personality-disorder 2016
 - MayoClinic organisation diseases-conditions/schizoid-personality-disorder 2016
 - MayoClinic staff diseases-conditions/narcissistic-personality-disorder/basics 2016
 - Cacciola JS, Alterman AI, McKay JR, Rutherford MJ. Psychiatric comorbidity in patients with substance use disorder: do not forget Axis II disorders. *Psychiatr Ann*. 2001; 31:321–331.
 - Mind We're a registered charity in England (no. 219830) and a registered company (no. 424348) in England and Wales. published in August 2016